

Sheep Meat Market Strategies

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Merino sheep at Las Albaidas farm, Córdoba

The consumption of sheep meat is decreasing Spain and mainly linked to some periods of the year such as Christmas holidays and celebrations. The consumption fall caused by dietary habit changes or market competition with other cheaper types of meat has led to the adoption of a strategy which differentiates the production of the Merino breed sheep in a nearby Córdoba farm. The strategy is linked to the lamb meat traceability and shows the way in which the lambs are reared as a product of extensive and transhumant livestock farming by using a QR code that links to an online platform.

Besides this innovative marketing strategy to increase added value of those products associated with the land use and care, the use of new technologies to certifying the traceability by using blockchain methods linked to lamb GPS technology, has allowed the consumer to find on the label itself, reliable information about the way the animals are reared, including maps of the grazed areas, the fencing types, the grazing time and even, real time grazing images... All this, allows to trace the origin and production conditions of sheep meat, thus improving the perception of quality but overall the fact that animals are part of the landscape and reducing fire risk linked to shrubland encroachment diminishing thanks to grazing and contributing to customer loyalty.

The certification of traceability through GPS provides greater knowledge of the product consumed, thus increasing the range of choice and confidence. Moreover, from the producer's point of view, it also means diversification of the sales channel.

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